

CAPACITIVE SOLAR COLLECTORS: THEORY, MODELING AND EXPERIMENTAL EVALUATION

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The mathematical model of the collector's operation is based on the energy exchange equations between the absorption surface, the heat carrier, and the storage element.

Experimental setup and modeling. For experimental verification of the developed model, a laboratory setup was created, including:

- Solar simulator for simulating natural radiation.
- Flat collector with integrated heat-accumulating module.
- Temperature and heat flow measurement system.

In parallel, a program code was developed for numerical calculation of heat exchange dynamics taking into account the storage capacity. The simulation results were compared with experimental data to validate the model.

Fig. 1. Graph of changes in the temperature of the coolant in the collector during the day.

As a result, it is possible to observe how, under the influence of solar inflow, the temperature of the collector rises in the daytime, and then decreases, approaching the ambient temperature (Fig. 1). Characteristics of the materials used. Liquids with high heat capacity were used as a heat transfer fluid, and phase change materials were used as a heat storage material, which makes it possible to increase the efficiency of energy storage with minimal dimensions of the collector.

Comparison of the experimental data with the results of numerical simulation showed a high correlation, which confirms the correctness of the chosen mathematical model. It was revealed that the integration of storage elements allows: - To increase the efficiency of heat energy

collection up to 15–20% under conditions of variable insolation. - Reduce temperature fluctuations of the heat transfer medium, providing a more stable heat supply. The analysis showed that the optimization of the collector geometry and the selection of heat-accumulating materials are key factors in improving the efficiency of the system. The results of the study are consistent with the data presented in the works [1-7] and expand them due to the integration of experimental data.